

SYNTHESIS AND CHARACTERIZATION OF Cu DOPED MANGANESE OXIDE NANOPARTICLES: EVALUATION OF ANTIBACTERIAL, ANTIFUNGAL, AND ANTIOXIDANT PROPERTIES

Hafiz Muhammad Sheraz^{*1}, Mahnoor¹, Abdul Waheed², Hafiz Muhammad Imran¹,
Muhammad Farooq³, Rabeea Kiran⁴, Muhammad Zubair¹,
Muhammad Ayub Khan⁵, Muhammad Azhar Latif⁶

¹Centre of Excellence in Solid State Physics, University of the Punjab, Lahore

²Institute of Physics Bahauddin Zakariya University, Multan

³Department of Chemistry, Khushal Khan Khattak University, Karak

⁴Institute of Microbiology, University of Veterinary and Animal Sciences, Lahore

⁵Department of Chemistry, University of Malakand, Pakistan

⁶Department of Pathology, Sargodha Medical College, Sargodha

*hafizsheraz302@gmail.com

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Corresponding Author: *
Hafiz Muhammad Sheraz

ABSTRACT

Introduction: Nanotechnology is being used in disease diagnosis, sensors, imaging, agriculture, chemistry, medication, catalysis, pollution degradation etc. Ag, Cu, and other metal nanoparticles have antimicrobial properties.

Aim: Current research was performed to assess the antibacterial, antifungal and antioxidant potential of Cu doped manganese oxide.

Material and Method: Hydrothermal synthesis was used to create the necessary nanoparticles for this investigation. The characterization of the produced material was done using powder X-ray diffraction (XRD), Fourier transform infrared spectroscopy (FTIR), and Energy Dispersive X-ray (EDX) to validate its nanoparticle property. Nanoparticles' antibacterial ability was tested on *Klebsiella pneumonia*, *E. coli*, and *Bacillus subtilis*. *Klebsiella pneumonia* was treated with Levofloxacin, Norfloxacin, Gentamicin, Chloramphenicol, Trimethoprim, Amoxicillin, and Ciprofloxacin antibiotics.

Results: Levofloxacin, Norfloxacin, Gentamicin, Chloramphenicol, Amoxicillin, and Ciprofloxacin all had antibacterial action according to the data, however Trimethoprim did not. The nanoparticles showed no antibacterial activity against *Klebsiella pneumonia* but were effective against *E. coli* and *Bacillus subtilis*. In the antifungal activity test, the nanoparticles inhibited the growth of *Fusarium equiseti*, with the zone of inhibition increasing over time, but had no effect on *Rhizopus stolonifer*. Additionally, the nanoparticles exhibited antioxidant activity, with a maximum of 67% at a concentration of 0.1 mg/2 ml, although this was less than the antioxidant activity of ascorbic acid, which showed 90% activity at the same concentration.

Conclusion: The Cu doped manganese oxide nanoparticles demonstrated promising biological activities, including antibacterial effects against *E. coli* and *Bacillus subtilis*, antifungal activity against *Fusarium equiseti*, and antioxidant properties. These findings suggest potential applications for these nanoparticles in biomedical and pharmaceutical fields, such as the development of new antimicrobial and antioxidant agents. However, further research is needed to fully explore their efficacy, safety, and potential uses.

INTRODUCTION:

Metal nanoparticles are used in catalysis optoelectronics, information storage, nanoelectronics, nanosensor, nanodevices, and optoelectronics. Copper nanoparticles have received greater attention than other metal particles due to their usage in catalysis, electrical, optics, and antibacterial, antifungal applications (Ponce & Klabunde, 2005). The methods of laser ablation, vacuum vapor deposition, chemical

reduction, microwave irradiation methods, and thermal reduction have all been used to create copper nanoparticles. It has been discovered that metal nanoparticles including Ag, Cu, and others exhibit antibacterial properties (Wei et al., 2010). Metal nanoparticles' power to interact to microbial membranes because of their high surface to volume ratio and small size, rather than just the release of metal ions from fluids, has been assigned as the cause of their

bactericidal activity. The antibacterial capabilities of metal nanoparticles are applied in many fields, such as food, water treatment, and medical equipment manufacturing (Ramyadevi et al., 2012). Yoon et al. (2007) reported that copper nanoparticles had an antimicrobial impact. Copper nanoparticles have been shown to exhibit antifungal and bacteriostatic effects by Cioffi et al. (2005).

Due to the unexpected prospective applications, copper nanoparticles have garnered a lot of consideration during the last few years. It is very important in many disciplines, including biology and nanomedicine. Copper is now employed as a fungicide, antimicrobial, antifouling, and water purifier (Borkow & Gabbay, 2004). Cu ions have been found to have important roles in collagen crosslinking in addition to having strong antibacterial capabilities. This contributes to the correct development of bone matrix. With regard to protecting the wound from infection and assisting in the development of bone matrix, copper ions may be anticipated to play a dual role in the healing of burn injuries (Qin et al., 2007). Chitosan fibers have been shown by Voruganti et al. (2005) to produce copper ions, which have a potent antibacterial effect on a number of bacterial species often present in wounds and on the skin. There are many ways to make copper nanoparticles (Cu-NPs), including the chemical reduction, metal vapour deposition (VVD), laser ablation, electro-chemical reduction, thermal decomposition, radiolytic reduction, mechanical attrition, microemulsion techniques, and sonochemical method chemical reduction. Chemical reductions are the most adaptable method for producing metal nanoparticles because it is quick and affordable. In order to stop the growth of the nanoparticles at the desired size and form, it typically entails reducing metal salts using reducing agents in some sort of solvent. The high propensity for oxidation of copper nanoparticles is one of the most difficult aspects of their manufacture.

Copper is far more air-sensitive than gold or silver, and the oxide phases are thermodynamically much stable. As a result, it is unavoidable that an oxide layer will grow on the surface of copper nanocomposite. Unless the entire process was carried out in an inert or reducing atmosphere, one can seldom ever discover a method in the literature that yields pure copper nanoparticles (Salzemann et al., 2004). Numerous bacteria, such as staphylococci and *Candida* species, can attach to the surface of medical implants (such as bone implants and vascular catheters) and form biofilms on the surfaces of biomaterials. One of the most frequent causes of nosocomial infections, post-operative wound, and bloodstream infections are multi-drug resistant microorganisms (Kruk et al., 2015). According to estimates, using copper's antibacterial qualities might cut the number of

illnesses by 15% yearly, saving roughly 150 million pounds a year (Noyce et al., 2007).

A third of the world's annual plant yield is thought to be lost each year to a variety of plant pathogenic illnesses and insect damage. In addition to viral and bacterial infections, fungal plant pathogens are the principal culprits behind the substantial yield loss. Fungi are responsible for significant economic losses to agriculture, a loss of food for human consumption, and severe, frequently fatal infections in both animals and humans. Molds and tiny fungus may grow and colonize a wide range of substrates, even in harsh climatic conditions (Warzecha et al., 2011). Many *Fusarium* species, including *Fusarium oxysporum*, *Fusarium culmorum*, and *Fusarium equiseti*. The creation of a novel fungicidal agent is required in light of the aforementioned problems, which result in a significant loss in agricultural output (Bramhanwade et al., 2016).

There is much work performed on Cu nanoparticle but not on the Cu doped manganese oxide nanoparticle, to cover this gap current study is an effort to add up in literature on the antifungal, antioxidant and antibacterial activity.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

The recent study was carried out at the Microbiology laboratory of University of the Punjab, Lahore. The materials used in this experiment were obtained from the different labs of University of the Punjab, Lahore.

Synthesis of nanoparticles

The sample was made by mixing 1.896 g KMnO_4 and 0.29 g $\text{Cu}(\text{NO}_3)_2$ in 100 mL of water, adding 1% SDS solution to the mixture, shifting it to an autoclave, and then adding 20 mL of HCl to the reaction mixture. After stirring the mixture for 30 minutes, the autoclave was shut and heated for 24 hours at 180 °C. After heating, the autoclave was opened and allowed to cool to room temperature. Dark powder was produced at the base of the autoclave. The extremely fine powdered substance was filtered and then washed with sufficient distilled water. The substance, which had been obtained as a dark powder, was examined for catalytic activity.

PXRD; 2θ (12.5, 17.3, 25.3, 33.5, 44.2, 50.6, 62.4, 71.6) D (42.21±4); FTIR cm^{-1} 532 ν (Mn-O) (1326, 1623). Percentage composition of elements (by EDX) found for $\text{Mn}_{0.82}\text{Cu}_{0.18}\text{O}_2$ is Mn 40.02; Cu 8.78; O 51.22.

Characterization of Cr doped manganese oxide

X-ray diffraction (XRD), Brunauer-Emmett-teller (BET), Fourier transform infrared spectroscopy (FTIR) and Scanning electron microscopy (SEM) analysis were used to characterize these materials to understand the properties and structures.

Antibacterial activity

University of the Punjab, Lahore supplied the *Klebsiella pneumonia* used in the in vitro antibacterial investigation. In accordance with the manufacturer's recommendations, the culture was revived. For 24 hours, *Klebsiella pneumonia* was allowed to develop in a 37°C incubator before being transferred to a 4°C refrigerator until required.

To prepare nutrient broth and agar one liter of clean water was used to uniformly combine 7.0 grams of the material. The mixture was then heated while being stirred, and the media was eventually entirely dissolved. After that, it was autoclaved for 15 minutes at 121°C.

The disc diffusion method was used to provide seven antibiotics (Levofloxacin, Norfloxacin, Gentamicin, Chloramphenicol, Trimethoprim, Amoxicillin, and Ciprofloxacin). Five distinct concentrations of nanoparticles (20 mg, 40 mg, 60 mg, 80 mg, and 100 mg) were collected using the disk diffusion method. The antibiotic Levofloxacin served as the standard.

The agar-well diffusion technique was used to test the nanoparticle's antibacterial action against the bacterial strains *Bacillus subtilis* and *E. coli*. Prior to use, the bacterial separates were first consistent to 0.5 McFarland standards (106 cfu mL⁻¹) by 18 hours of culture in nutritional broth. 0.5 mL of 0.048 M BaCl₂ was added to 99.5 mL of 0.36 N H₂SO₄ to create the 0.5 McFarland standards. Barium sulfate turbidity standard (4-6 mL) was measured and placed in a test tube with a screw lid.

Nutrient agar (MERCK) was mixed in 100 mL of distilled water with a pH of 7.0 to make the nutrient agar medium, after that it was autoclaved. It was allowable to cool to 45 °C. 75 mL of seeded nutritional agar was moved into petri dishes and let to stabilize. A germ-free cork borer with a 6 mm diameter was used to drill wells into the agar. 0.025, 0.05, 0.075, and 0.1mg/ml of Cu-doped manganese oxide were added to the wells before being incubated at 37 °C for around 2 hours. Parallel controls using the appropriate solvents to fill fully were set up. After 24 hours, zones of inhibition on the plates were looked for. The effects were contrasted with Ciprofloxacin at a 5 microgram concentration.

Antifungal activity

Using the agar well diffusion technique, the produced NPs' antifungal activity was evaluated. To examine the antifungal effectiveness of certain NPs, fungi cultures were cultivated on potato dextrose medium. To make potato dextrose agar, 500ml of water that had been distilled, 10g of agar, 125g of starch from potatoes, and 10g of sugar were mixed together. Streptomycin was also administered to stop any bacterial development.

The autoclaved dextrose agar made from potatoes was heated to 121°C and fifteen kilograms under pressure for 15 minutes. Plates were covered with potato dextrose agar, which was then let to set. After the culture plates had dried in the laminar airflow chamber, wells were drilled into the agar plate with a 5mm conventional cork borer. University of the Punjab's Botany Department has identified fungal cultures from papaya and persimmon called *Rhizopus* and *Fusarium*. The relevant wells received various doses of NPs (0.025, 0.05, 0.075, and 0.1 mg/ml). Fungicide was used as the control strategy. The plates were then sealed and kept at 252°C for three days. Three, five, and seven days later, results were seen.

Antioxidant activity

9.85mg of DPPH was taken in measuring flask and then some methanol was added to dissolve DPPH. After the complete dissolve of DDPH in methanol and no solid particles remained then 50ml of methanol was added and it was shaken thoroughly. The obtained solution was placed in dark cabinet at room temperature for 30 minutes. With a small alteration, the process was carried out in accord with Bhakya et al. (2016) Using the constant radical DPPH, the capacity of Cu doped manganese oxide and ascorbic acid to scavenge free radicals was assessed. A freshly generated 1 ml of DPPH solution was combined with 1.5 ml of various amounts of distilled water (0.02, 0.04, 0.06, 0.08, 0.1, 0.15, and 0.2mg/2ml) and vortexed energetically. After that, the mixture was let to be seated for 30 minutes in the dark at room temperature. With the use of an UVeVis spectrophotometer, the absorbance was measured at 517 nm. 1.5 ml of methanol was used as a blank solution, and DPPH (all the reagents except the sample) was used as a control. The percentage of inhibition, which was calculated using the following formula, used to represent the free radical scavenging action.

$$\% \text{ of scavenging} = \frac{P_c - P_s}{P_c} \times 100$$

Where P_s is the absorption of the CuNPs/ascorbic acid mixture and P_c is the absorbance of the control.

RESULTS

Characterization

PXRD Results: The PXRD results reveal the presence of -MnO₂ as the predominant phase and the minor inclusion of CrO₃ and MnCrO₄. The acquired patterns demonstrated that the peak for -MnO₂ had less strength as the incorporation of Cr increased under the influence of the peaks for CrO₃. Tetragonal in shape and belonging to the P4₂/mmn space group, -MnO₂'s primary phase.

Figure 1: PXRD patterns of Nanomaterials

For prepared sample, the computed average crystallite size for series-VI was 42.21 ± 4 . It has been considered that the chromium incorporation increased crystallite size and hence led to crystal stress. The dislocation density values indicate that series-V nanomaterials have superior stability due to their smaller crystallite size, reduced defect extent, and reduced defect extent. The values of the crystalline volume show that the chromium ions are properly incorporated

into the samples' regular lattice positions. Chromium ions cause an increase in crystal strain and crystal imperfection when they are present in the structure of $\alpha\text{-MnO}_2$. The lattice contraction discovered during the calculation of the lattice parameters may be the cause of the positive tensile micro strain values seen in nanomaterials. The PXRD results further support the samples' monocrystalline nature and the elemental makeup shown in table 1.

Table 1: PXRD parameters of nanocatalyst

Sample	Cu doped manganese oxide
Found Composition	$\text{Mn}_{0.82}\text{Cu}_{0.18}\text{O}_2$
Average Crystallite Size D (nm)	42.21 ± 4
Volume $V=D^3$	59876
Dislocation Density $\times 10^{-3} \text{ (nm)}^{-2}$ (δ)	4.11×10^{-4}
Micro Strain (ϵ)	0.082

SEM Results: The features of nanomaterials are described in Table 2 and their SEM pictures are displayed in Figure 2. This set' SEM pictures demonstrated the amorphous nature of

nanocatalysts. The produced nanocatalysts resemble rod-like structures in form. Table showed the prepared nanocatalysts morphological characteristics as determined by SEM.

Table 2: SEM results of the prepared nanoparticles

Sample	Cu doped manganese oxide
Material Nature	Amorphous
Dispersity	Heterodisperse
Structural Appearance	Rod - like Structure

Figure 2: SEM image of NPs

BET Results: The specific surface area of nanocatalysts was calculated using the multipoint BET approach, and the pore structure of the nanomaterials was estimated using the DFT method, as shown in the table 3. Nanocatalysts had a surface area that was almost 38-48 m²/g. Sample demonstrated a higher surface area per

gram (48.06 m²) although MH60 had a lower pore volume per gram (38.22 vs. 0.035), demonstrating that nanomaterials appear to be microporous in nature. It was observed that values of the constant C were less than 100, indicating the interaction of solid adsorbate and adsorbent.

Table 3: BET Characteristics of Prepared Nanocatalysts

Sample	Cu doped manganese oxide
Surface Area (S _{BET}) (m ² /g)	19.12
Pore Volume (V _m) (cc/g)	0.022
Pore Width (nm)	4.814
Constant	44.12

FTIR Results: All of the distinctive signals of the samples have been visible in the FTIR spectra of the sample. In the 1000 to 500 cm⁻¹ range, the bending and stretching vibrations of individual

metal and oxygen bonds were seen. Here, the FTIR spectra agree with the findings. High structural Symmetry is revealed by a simple FTIR pattern.

Figure 3: FTIR Spectra of sample

Antibacterial assay

The growth of *Klebsiella pneumonia* was slightly inhibited by the antibiotics. The table 4 below displays how the seven different antibiotics affect the growth of *Klebsiella pneumoniae*. Levofloxacin,

Norfloxacin, Gentamicin, Chloramphenicol, Amoxicillin and Ciprofloxacin showed antibacterial activity but Trimethoprim did not showed antibacterial property *Klebsiella pneumoniae*.

Table 4: Zone diameters of antibiotics against *Klebsiella pneumoniae*

Antibiotics	Symbols	Concentrations	Susceptible	Intermediate susceptible	Resistant	Finding	Result
1.Levofloxacin	LEV	5µg	≥17	14-16	≤13	25mm	Susceptible
2.Norfloxacin	NOR	10µg	≥17	13-16	≤12	7mm	Resistant
3.Gentamicin	CN	10µg	≥15	13-14	≤12	10mm	Resistant
4.Chloramphenicol	C	30µg	≥18	13-17	≤12	18mm	Susceptible
5.Trimethoprim	SXT	25µg	≥16	11-15	≤10	No zone	Resistant
6.Amoxicillin	AML	10µg	≥18	14-17	≤13	10mm	Resistant
7.Ciprofloxacin	CIP	5µg	≥21	16-20	≤15	6mm	Resistant

Figure 4: Effect of antibiotics on the growth of *Klebsiella pneumoniae*

The antibacterial activity of nanoparticle was demonstrated by using different concentrations (20, 40, 60, 80 and 100mg) of nanoparticles submerged in whatman paper against *Klebsiella*

pneumonia and Levofloxacin was used as a positive control. The outcomes of the experiment demonstrated that Levofloxacin has more antibacterial potential than nanoparticles.

Figure 5: Effect of nanoparticles on the growth of *Klebsiella pneumonia*

The findings of the experiments showed that the Cu doped manganese oxide nanoparticle possesses antibacterial properties because the growth of *E. coli* and *Bacillus subtilis* was inhibited. Nanoparticles were employed in four distinct concentrations (0.025, 0.05, 0.075, and 0.1) for antibacterial activity. Ciprofloxacin served as the

activity's positive control. Zones of inhibition varied depending on concentration. In all concentrations of *Bacillus subtilis*, the same zone of inhibition existed. The same zone of inhibition was present in *E. coli* at concentrations of 0.05, 0.075, and 0.1, and the least at 0.025.

Table 5: The antibacterial effect of Cu doped manganese oxide on *Bacillus subtilis* and *E.coli*

	Sample	<i>Bacillus subtilis</i>	<i>E.coli</i>
		Zone in mm	Zone in mm
Cu60	0.025	7	6
	0.05	7	7
	0.075	7	7
	1	7	7
Positive control	(Ciprofloxacin)	34	37

Figure 6: Effect of Cu doped manganese oxide on the growth of *Bacillus subtilis*

Figure 7: Graph represents the antibacterial property of NPs against *Bacillus subtilis*

Figure 8: Effect of Cu doped manganese oxide on the growth of *E. coli*

Figure 9: Graph represents the antibacterial potential of nanoparticle against E.coli

Antifungal assay

Results of antifungal activity were seen on the third, fifth, and seventh days. For the *Fusarium*, the maximum zone of inhibition was seen on day 7 and the minimum on day 3. The growth of *Rhizopus* did not exhibit any impediment. Zones of inhibition were 0.2, 0.9, 1.0, and 3 on the third day of *Fusarium* observation at doses of 0.025, 0.05, 0.075, and 0.1, respectively. The concentration of 0.1 produced the largest zone of inhibition and 0.025 the smallest. Zones of

inhibition were 1.9, 2.3, 1.9, and 2.2 on the fifth day of *Fusarium* observation at concentrations of 0.025, 0.05, 0.075, and 0.1, respectively. The concentration of 0.05 produced the largest zone of inhibition, while 0.025 and 0.075 produced the smallest. The zones of inhibition for the *Fusarium* on the seventh day of observation were 2.5, 3, 2.4, and 2.5, respectively, for the doses of 0.025, 0.05, 0.075, and 0.1. The concentrations of 0.1 and 0.025 had the highest zone of inhibition and 0.075 had the lowest.

Table 6: Table shows the concentration of nanoparticles and the zone of inhibition of the *Fusarium* on 3rd, 5th and 7th day

<i>Fusarium</i>	Concentration	Day 3	Day 5	Day 7
	0.025	0.2	1.9	2.5
	0.05	0.9	2.3	3
	0.075	1.0	1.9	2.4
	0.1	3	2.2	2.5

Figure 10: Control group of Cu NPs

Figure 11: Cu NPs at different concentration against *Fusarium equesiti* after 3rd day of incubation

Figure 12: Cu NPs at different concentration against *Fusarium equesiti* after 5th day of incubation

Figure 13: Cu NPs at different concentration against *Fusarium equesiti* after 7th day of incubation

Figure 14: Graph represents the antifungal property of NPs against *Fusarium equiseti*

The development of *Rhizopus* was not affected by the antifungal properties of Cu doped manganese oxide nanoparticles. It began to expand on the third day and continued to grow the same on day five and seven.

Figure 15: Control group of *Rhizopus*

Figure 16: Cu NPs at different concentrations against *Rhizopus* after 3rd day of incubation

Figure 17: Cu NPs at different concentration against *Rhizopus* after 5th day of incubation

Figure 18: Cu NPs at different concentration against *Rhizopus* after 7th day of incubation

Antioxidant assay

The findings of the antioxidant activity test support the antioxidant activity of ascorbic acid and copper oxide nanoparticles (CuO NPs). The ascorbic acid has 90% antioxidant activity at the same concentration, but the Cu oxide NPs had a

maximum antioxidant activity of 67% at a concentration of 0.1 mg/2 ml. Cu oxide NPs have a 9% antioxidant activity at a concentration of 0.04 mg/2 ml. The findings demonstrated that compared to ascorbic acid, Cu NPs has reduced antioxidant activity.

Table 7: The table shows the concentrations of Cu doped manganese oxide used in this experiment and the percentage of antioxidant property of Cu doped manganese oxide at given concentrations

Concentrations	Test Sample	Ascorbic acid
0.02	16%	81%
0.04	9%	83%
0.06	33%	85%
0.08	55%	86%
0.1	67%	90%
0.15	31%	87%
0.2	30%	85%

Figure 19: The graph shows the concentrations of Cu doped manganese oxide used in this experiment and the percentage of antioxidant property of Cu doped manganese oxide at given concentrations.

DISCUSSION

The goal of the current work was to evaluate the Cu doped manganese oxide nanoparticle's antioxidant, antimicrobial, and antifungal activities. Mir Alam et al. (2022) evaluated the antioxidant properties of a new copper-zinc-manganese trimetal oxide nanocomposite. The produced nanocomposite exhibits significant antioxidant activity, with scavenging activity measured at 31, 62, 125, 250, and 500 g/mL, respectively, to be 76.58 0.30, 76.89 0.44, 81.41 30, 82.58 0.32, and 84.36 0.09%. The outcomes demonstrate that nanoparticles' (NPs) antioxidant activity was concentration-dependent.

On *Fusarium* and *Rhizopus*, antifungal action was demonstrated. For this, *Fusarium* and *Rhizopus* were removed from papaya and persimmon. In petri dishes, various NP concentrations (0.025, 0.05, 0.075, and 0.1 mg/ml) and fungicide were applied. Days 3, 5, and 7 saw observations on the culture. On day 3, the concentration of 0.1 showed the highest zone of inhibition and 0.025 the lowest. Day 5 revealed a maximal inhibition zone at 0.1 concentration and a minimum at 0.025. On day 7, the maximum zone of inhibition was at doses of 0.01 and the minimum

was at 0.025. The outcomes demonstrated that the corresponding NPs have an antifungal impact on *Fusarium*. Bramhanwade et al. (2016) found concurrent outcomes when employing Cu nanoparticles to combat *F. equiseti*, *Fusarium. culmorum*, and *F. oxysporum* were chosen as the three different crop harmful fungus against which the in vitro antifungal efficacy of produced copper NPs was investigated. It's interesting to note that the investigated crop pathogenic fungus was effectively combated by copper nanoparticles. Amphotericin B was employed as a typical antifungal drug for antifungal action. The zone of inhibition for copper nanoparticles against *F. equiseti* was 25 mm in diameter, with *F. culmorum* (19 mm) and *F. oxysporum* (20 mm) following closely after. The Kirby-Bauer disk diffusion method was used to assess the antifungal activity (Gittard et al., 2010). Three duplicates of the research were kept on file. In vitro antifungal action of chemically produced copper NPs in combination with the commercial antifungal drug Bavistin was also reported by Kanhed et al. (2014) against four different plant pathogenic fungus, including *P. destructive*, *F. oxysporum*, *A.*

alternata, and *C. lunata*. All of the plant pathogenic fungus that was used in their research was actively inhibited by copper nanoparticles. To find out the antifungal characteristics, Kasana et al. (2016) created copper nanoparticles in a range of diameters from 5 to 280 nm. Copper nanoparticles produced biologically exhibit potent antifungal properties that stop the spread of dangerous fungus. It has also been observed that copper nanoparticles have antifungal efficacy against the pathogenic fungus *Phytophthora infestans*, *Fusarium culmorum*, *Fusarium graminearum*, and *Fusarium oxysporum*. The current study's findings indicate that the NPs had no impact on *Rhizopus* growth.

The outcomes of the bactericidal rate of several Cu-doped materials were reported by Cui et al. (2015). A high amount of antibacterial action is indicated by the bactericidal rate value. The bactericidal rate in Cu-doped samples was substantially higher at 15 minutes than it was in the pure MgO sample. According to Renné et al. (2017) PAA-CuI nanoparticles are a useful addition to glass ionomer-based products since they significantly boost the antibacterial properties of those materials. Using optical density at 600 nm and a comparison of the size of the inhibitory zone diameter, Samavati et al. (2016) reported the antibacterial action of the Cu-doped ZnO NPs generated by the sol-gel method against *Escherichia coli* (Gram negative bacterium) cultures. It is discovered that ZnO nanoparticles, whether pure or doped, exhibit adequate antibacterial activity, which increases with Cu doping.

CONCLUSION

The current research was carried out to determine the effect of Cu doped manganese oxide nanoparticles on antioxidant, antibacterial and antifungal activity. The antibacterial potential was tested against *Klebsiella pneumonia*, *Bacillus subtilis*, and *E. coli*. The growth of *E. coli* and *Bacillus subtilis* was inhibited by nanoparticles. The antifungal potent was tested against *Fusarium* and *Rhizopus*, the nanoparticles inhibited the growth of *Fusarium* but no effect on the growth of *Rhizopus*. The results of antioxidant activity of nanoparticles were compared with the ascorbic acid. The antioxidant results confirmed that nanoparticle has more antioxidant property as compared to ascorbic acid. The results of the recent activities showed that CuNPs have significant antioxidant, antibacterial and antifungal property. It is concluded that nanoparticles have significant importance in biomedical fields and can be used to cope with all these hazards.

AUTHORS CONTRIBUTION

Conceptualization: HMS, M, AW, HMI
Methodology: HMS, M, AW, HMI, RK
Formal analysis: HMS, RK, MZ, MF

Writing, review and editing: HMS, MAK, MAL, MF

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